

Place-based Land Policy and Firm Productivity: Evidence from China's Eastern-Inland Regional Border*

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Abstract

We study the effect of China's inland-favoring land policy on firm-level productivity using a research design that combines difference-in-differences and regression discontinuity at the policy border. We find that the inland-favoring land policy decreased the firm-level productivity gap between more developed eastern regions and underdeveloped inland regions. More specifically, the relative changes are mainly due to slower productivity growth in eastern firms rather than faster productivity growth in inland firms. We find that this policy increased land costs, decreased new firm entry, and consequently reduced agglomeration and knowledge spillovers in the east. In response, eastern firms reduced their R&D expenditures, potentially harming their long-run efficiency.

Keywords: Place-based Policy; Land Policy; Regional Inequality; China; Firm Productivity

JEL Classification Numbers: R58, R52, D24;

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1 Introduction

Many countries implement place-based policies to promote balanced national development by helping underdeveloped regions, including cash transfers, tax reductions, and land allocation regulations (Neumark and Simpson, 2015). However, such policies, especially land policies, can lead to spatial misallocation, particularly in the presence of spatial frictions. Fang et al. (2022) provides a quantitative analysis showing that the 2003 inland-favoring land policy implemented in China led to spatial misallocation of labor and production. Yet, direct evidence at the firm level is missing. In this paper, we fill this gap by empirically examining the impacts of this Chinese place-based land allocation policy on firm-level productivity.

How was this place-based policy designed? In China, all urban land is state-owned, and the central government enforces strict quotas on construction land for each prefecture. Following the 1978 reforms, these quotas were allocated based on demand, primarily benefiting the rapidly expanding eastern coastal regions. However, the growing economic disparity between the eastern regions and the rest of the country became a significant concern. As a result, in 2003 the policy was dramatically shifted from a demand-driven approach to a development-promoting strategy, reallocating land supply quotas from the east to inland regions. This inland-favoring land supply policy has been in effect ever since. In this paper, we aim to find the direct causal effect of this policy change on the measured productivity of firms.

A typical identification problem is that eastern firms are usually very different from those in other regions in terms of both observed and unobserved characteristics. To alleviate this endogeneity issue, we employ a method combining border Regression Discontinuity Design (Black, 1999) and the Difference-in-Differences approach (RD-DID). The basic idea is that firms within a minimal bandwidth along the border are very similar, no matter which side they are located on. Thus, firm-level TFP should have similar time trends. This allows us to implement an RD-DID strategy on these border firms to identify the effects of the inland-favoring land policy at the firm level. Compared with the prefecture-level regression, the advantage of this firm-level regression is that it exploits more variation and provides detailed micro evidence.

We show that the inland-favoring policy reduced the firm-level TFP gap between firms in the

eastern and inland regions by approximately 8%.¹ The results remain robust across various robustness exercises. Moreover, we do not observe significant TFP improvements among inland firms, which means that the relative changes could be mainly due to slower productivity growth among eastern firms rather than faster productivity growth among inland firms. Our empirical analysis demonstrates that the inland-favoring land policy narrowed the productivity gap between eastern and inland firms by adversely affecting eastern firms without significantly benefiting inland firms, suggesting that land constraints could be a potential cause.

These changes in firm TFP patterns could stem from two channels. First, the policy may have directly impeded the productivity of eastern firms by constraining their land usage, slowing their innovation, and diminishing agglomeration benefits. We term this the "direct effect." Second, a more restrictive land policy in eastern regions could precipitate the exit of lower productivity firms from the market or compel them to downscale their business below the survey threshold of the NIED (survey sample) or even cease to operate. We refer to this as the "selection effect."

We investigate these two channels separately and find that the direct effect dominates. The inland-favoring land policy significantly increased eastern land prices, forcing firms to cut their costs by reducing their R&D expenditures. Additionally, the land supply limitation deterred more firms from entering eastern regions and potentially decreased agglomeration effects. On the contrary, we find no evidence for the selection effect. Consequently, we find that the inland-favoring land supply policy narrowed the productivity gap between inland firms and eastern firms by reducing the productivity growth of eastern firms. This reduction in productivity growth is accompanied by a decline in new firm entry and a decrease in R&D expenditure among eastern firms, potentially harming their long-term development.

However, this policy affects both equality and efficiency. We explicitly discuss this tradeoff in [Fang et al. \(2022\)](#). We find that this policy actually decreased the wages of workers from underdeveloped regions: exactly those it was designed to help. In [Fang et al. \(2022\)](#), we conduct a prefecture-level empirical analysis and use a spatial general equilibrium model to show the effects on macroeconomic aggregates and income distribution. The quantitative analysis shows that, although the government achieved the goal of shrinking the regional eastern-inland gap, it

¹This result is consistent with the prefecture-level regression result in [Fang et al. \(2022\)](#).

came at a substantial cost of spatial misallocation of production and labor. The distortion in the land market is transmitted to the labor market by decreasing firm labor demand and increasing housing costs in developed eastern regions. Thus, this inland-favoring land policy actually decreased the income of workers from underdeveloped regions by hurting their opportunities to migrate east.

Literature Our study contributes to three strands of literature. First, we investigate the direct causal effect of place-based land policy on firm productivity in a developing country. Many studies have investigated different kinds of place-based policies in developed countries from different perspectives (Neumark and Simpson, 2015), including enterprise zones (Neumark and Kolko, 2010; Ham et al., 2011; Busso, Gregory, and Kline, 2013), discretionary grants (Crozet, Mayer, and Mucchielli, 2004; Devereux, Griffith, and Simpson, 2007), infrastructure investment (Kline and Moretti, 2014; Becker, Egger, and Von Ehrlich, 2010), and community development (Eriksen and Rosenthal, 2010; Accetturo and De Blasio, 2012). This paper extends this literature by considering a large-scale place-based policy in a developing country.

Second, our study contributes to the extensive literature on spatial misallocation. The literature has investigated various frictions that result in spatial misallocation, including housing constraints (Hsieh and Moretti, 2019), tax policies (Fajgelbaum et al., 2019), migration frictions (Wu and You, 2023), farmland frictions (Fu, Xu, and Zhang, 2021; Yu, 2019), and various combinations of the above frictions (Li, Ma, and Tang, 2021; Deng et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2019). We further investigate the spatial misallocation of land supply due to urban land regulation and its consequences for firm productivity growth.

Third, this paper contributes to the literature on migration and regional development in China. Other scholars have investigated the Hukou restriction and regional trade barriers (Tombe and Zhu, 2019; Pi and Chen, 2019), international trade and labor mobility (Ma and Tang, 2020; Tian, 2018; Fan, 2019; Zi, 2020), housing constraints (Fang and Huang, 2022), air quality (Khanna et al., 2021), and local public services for migrants (Sieg, Yoon, and Zhang, 2021; Huang, 2020). This study contributes to the literature by connecting land misallocation and firm productivity.

2 Background and Data

2.1 Background

In China, agricultural land is collectively owned by villages, while urban land is state-owned. Citizens cannot own land privately. To convert agricultural land to urban use, the local government first collects it from rural collectives (villages). Construction companies then purchase "use rights" from the local government to develop urban land. As a result, the central government can tightly control urban expansion by setting land usage plans for each region. Each year, each prefecture receives an annual quota for new urban construction land, which was primarily based on demand before 2003. Thus, developed coastal regions would receive more land quota and supply more construction land.

However, after 2003, the central government changed its strategy to balance development across regions due to the continuously growing regional development gap between eastern and inland regions. Specifically, they aimed to encourage the economic growth of inland regions by increasing land quotas for underdeveloped inland provinces (Lu and Xiang, 2016; Han and Lu, 2017; Fu, Xu, and Zhang, 2021; Fang et al., 2022). Land quota sets a tight constraint on land usage each year. Figure 1 illustrates the history of eastern and inland land quotas. A pivotal shift is observable post-2003. While eastern regions experienced reduced quotas, inland regions saw a substantial increase. This period marked a cessation of land quota growth in eastern areas, contrasted with encouraging growth in inland regions.

2.2 Data

The primary dataset utilized in this study is the National Industrial Enterprise Database (NIED), published by the National Bureau of Statistics. This database includes all state-owned and non-state-owned enterprises classified as "above scale" (main business revenue exceeding 5 million RMB, which is about \$700,000 USD), accounting for over 90% of all industrial production in China from 1998 to 2007. The dataset provides comprehensive enterprise-level information, including firm name, four-digit industry category, year of establishment, number of employees, total pay-

Figure 1: Urban Land Quotas Before and After 2003

Notes: This figure shows the allocated quota of urban land in the inland and eastern regions of China each year. Data sources are the National Bureau of Statistics of China, Statistical Yearbook of China's Land and Resources (1999–2007), and Yearbook of China's Land (1999–2007).

roll, and total fixed assets. To address potential data anomalies, we implement a 1% censoring process to exclude abnormal observations. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the enterprise data. Our primary TFP measurement is based on the OP (Olley and Pakes, 1992) estimation method. Additionally, we calculate TFP using the LP (Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003) method in Appendix A, which yields similar results.

Furthermore, we employ other datasets to provide additional evidence. We utilize the China Land and Resources Statistical Yearbook to obtain province-level land quota data. Published by the Ministry of Land and Resources of China, this yearbook contains data on land, minerals, oil, natural gas, and various other natural resources. Unfortunately, prefecture-level construction land quota data remains confidential and is not publicly available. We also use the Firm Registration Data in China to investigate firm entry behavior. This comprehensive dataset includes information on all Chinese firms, such as their industry, location, and entry dates.

Table 1: **Summary Statistics**

Variable	Description	Observations	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Median	Max
Ln(tfp_op)	TFP(OP)	877383	3.25	1.02	-0.04	3.27	5.63
Ln(tfp_lp)	TFP(LP)	877383	6.36	1.09	3.08	6.32	9.02
Ln(output)	Ln(1k yuan)	877383	8.62	1.29	5.31	8.51	12.22
Ln(wage)	Ln(1k yuan)	876147	2.39	0.63	0.39	2.41	4.14
Age	Year	877383	9.66	9.22	1	7	48
Employee	Person	877383	192.37	293.80	12	97	1985
East	Dummy	877383	0.80	0.40	0	1	1
Firm Distance	Km	877383	76.06	102.32	-199.99	102.52	200

Notes: East is a dummy variable set to 1 if the firm is in the eastern region. Firm distance is from the firm’s location to the east–inland provincial boundary, which is positive for eastern firms and negative for inland firms. All chosen observations are within 200 km of the boundary.

3 Main Empirical Analysis

We empirically analyze how the inland-favoring land supply policy affected firm performance, emphasizing the effects on firm-level TFP. We provide causal evidence that this policy shrank the TFP gap between eastern and inland firms. This reduction in the gap can be primarily attributed to the decreased TFP of eastern firms.

3.1 Empirical Specification

Our main empirical strategy in analyzing firm TFP combines a Border Regression Discontinuity Design as in [Black \(1999\)](#) and a Difference-in-Differences approach (RD-DID). The basic idea is to first compare firm TFP on the eastern and inland sides of the border. Then, we compare this border TFP difference over time, particularly before and after the year when the central government implemented the inland-favoring land supply policy. If the time trend of TFP is similar in the neighborhood of the border, the DID design can identify the policy effect. [Figure 2](#) shows the location of the boundary between the eastern and inland regions of China. Red dots represent firms on the eastern side of the boundary. Black dots represent firms on the inland side of the boundary. We use the region definitions published by the National Bureau of Statistics of China. Specifically, we categorize northeastern provinces as inland.

Figure 2: China's Eastern-Inland Boundary

Notes: The boundary is between eastern provinces and their inland neighbors. Red dots represent firms on the eastern side of the boundary. Black dots represent firms on the inland side of the boundary (To avoid confusion, the black dots on the eastern coastline are just islands, which are not part of our firm sample). The data source is the National Bureau of Statistics of China.

For firm i at border segment b in city c and year t , we have the following regression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln(y_{ibt}) = & \alpha + \beta_1 East_{ibt} + \beta_2 f(Dist_{ibt}) + \beta_3 East_{ibt} \times f(Dist_{ibt}) \\
 & + Post2003 \times [\delta_1 East_{ibt} + \delta_2 f(Dist_{ibt}) + \delta_3 East_{ibt} \times f(Dist_{ibt})] \\
 & + \beta_4 X_{ct-1} + \phi_{bt} + \gamma_t + \psi_i + \epsilon_{ibct}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where y_{ibt} is the log TFP of firm i . $East_{ibt}$ is a dummy that equals one if the firm is located on the eastern side of the border, which carries a subscript t since firms can change their locations over time (although only very few do so). $f(Dist_{ibt})$ is a smooth function of the distance between the firm and the border, and $Post2003$ is a dummy that equals one if t is after 2003 (including 2003). X_{ct-1} is a set of lagged city-level control variables, including the log of GDP, the log of population,

the log of city area, and the value added to the service sector. ϕ_{bt} is the border segment fixed effect for the firm at time t . We divide the border into five segments of equal length and assign each firm to the nearest segment. γ_t is the year fixed effect. ψ_i is the firm fixed effect.

This regression combines RD and DID methods. First, consider the first three terms (except the intercept), that is, $\beta_1 East_{ibt} + \beta_2 f(Dist_{ibt}) + \beta_3 East_{ibt} \times f(Dist_{ibt})$. This comprises a border regression discontinuity design, with the running variable being the distance to the border. Using only the observations within a small bandwidth, we assume that firms just on the eastern side of the border are very similar to firms just on the inland side. By fitting a smooth function $f(Dist)$, β_1 captures the effect of being in the eastern region on outcome variable y . This study uses two fitting functions: local linear regression and linear regression.

Second, we add interactions between the post-2003 dummy and all previous RD terms. Coefficient δ_1 then denotes the policy effect, which is interpreted as the change in the eastern region's TFP premium over the inland region before and after the 2003 inland-favoring land allocation policy. This is a difference-in-differences estimation. The first difference is between the eastern and inland regions (at the border). The second difference is between the before-policy and the after-policy periods.

It is important to clarify that the inland-favoring land policy can potentially affect the TFP levels of both regions. Therefore, the regression coefficient should be interpreted as the policy's effect on the regional gap (relative level) rather than on the absolute level of TFP for either region.

3.2 Regression Assumptions Validation

We validate our regression method by checking several important assumptions. First, we investigate the existence of the boundary discontinuity by drawing an RD figure. Panel A of Figure 3 shows data before 2003, and panel B data after 2003. The x-axis displays the distance of firms from the boundary, with a positive distance indicating firms located on the eastern side. The y-axis displays firm-level TFP, calculated using the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. This reveals a distinct discontinuity along the eastern-inland border in both panels. Notably, this gap narrowed following the implementation of the 2003 inland-favoring land policy.

Figure 3: **Regression Discontinuity Changes**

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP calculated using the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The smoothing function is linear. The bandwidth is 40 km from the border.

Second, we investigate the eastern and inland time trends of firm TFP. Our regression specification assumes that firms on the eastern and inland sides of the border should share a similar time trend. Figure 4 shows the time trends of firm-level TFP. The black line represents the average TFP for firms in the developed eastern region, and the grey line is the average TFP for inland firms. The dashed vertical line is located in 2003 when the inland-favoring land policy was implemented. We find no evidence of divergent time trends in firm productivity before the policy. Despite the 2003 policy's aim to boost inland development, we do not observe a corresponding increase in the growth rate of inland TFP. Instead, the policy seems to have stymied the growth of eastern TFP.

Finally, we implement a traditional event study regression to investigate the evolution of the eastern region effect over time. We take 2003 as the baseline year and then run the following

Figure 4: **Time Trends of Firm TFP**

Notes: This figure shows the time trends of firm-level TFP calculated using the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The black line is average TFP in the developed eastern region, and the grey line is average inland TFP. The dashed vertical line indicates the implementation of the inland-favoring land policy. TFP is calculated using only firms within 40km of the border. Firm-level TFP followed similar trends before the policy.

regression for the event study:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln(y_{ibct}) = & \alpha + \beta_1 East_{ibt} + \beta_2 f(Dist_{ibt}) + \beta_3 East_{ibt} \times f(Dist_{ibt}) \\
 & + \sum_{s \neq 2003} \mathbf{1}(s = t) \times [\delta_{1s} East_{ibt} + \delta_{2s} f(Dist_{ibt}) + \delta_{3s} East_{ibt} \times f(Dist_{ibt})] \\
 & + \beta_4 X_{ct-1} + \phi_{bt} + \gamma_t + \psi_i + \epsilon_{ibct}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

We plot the evolution of the coefficient δ_{1s} over time s in [Figure 5](#), illustrating the changing effect of the eastern region over time, with 95% confidence intervals. We choose a linear smoothing function. We find that all coefficients are very close to zero before 2003. They became statistically and economically distinguishable from zero only after the policy was implemented. The results from this event study confirm that there is no pre-trend in our data. These figures also give us a preview of the main results. After the central government imposed the inland-favoring land policy in 2003, there was a decrease in the firm productivity gap between the eastern and inland

Figure 5: **Event Study - TFP (OP)**

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP calculated using the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The bandwidth is 40 km from the border. The corresponding confidence interval is 95%.

regions.

3.3 Main Empirical Results

Table 2 shows the regression results based on TFP. In the first column, we use local linear regression as our fitting function. In the second column, we change the fitting function to be a global first-order polynomial (linear). We use the optimal bandwidth for the local linear fit based on [Imbens and Kalyanaraman \(2012\)](#). The bandwidth we use for the linear fit is 40 km. We also try other bandwidths, and the results are similar. Please refer to Appendix A for details. We find that the reduction in land supply after 2003 reduced the measured TFP of eastern firms relative to inland firms by about 8%.

Table 2: **RD-DID Results on TFP (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0798** (0.0356)	-0.0761* (0.0426)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,250	100,054
R-squared	0.1203	0.1161

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD case is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km around the raw boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

3.4 Province-level Quota Regressions

To further validate our main results, we implement a province-level quota regression as follows:

$$\ln(Prod_{ijt}) = \alpha + \delta_1 Post2003_t \times QS_j + \phi_i + \gamma_t + \delta_2 X_{it} + \delta_3 X_{jt-1} + \epsilon_{jt} \quad (3)$$

where the subscripts i , j , and t refer to firm, province, and year, respectively. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP. QS_j represents the change in the quota share of the province where firm i is located before and after the policy (the 2000-2002 share minus the 2003-2007 share). This measures the exposure to the inland-favoring land supply policy. We also control for firm fixed effects (ϕ_i), year fixed effects (γ_t), tax and subsidy policies (X_{it}), and lagged city-level control variables (X_{jt-1}). While it would be better to run this regression at the city level, city-level land quota data is unavailable in China, so we have to use province-level quota data instead.

Table 3 shows that firms in provinces more exposed to the 2003 policy experienced a reduction in TFP relative to firms in less exposed provinces. This provides direct evidence that the 2003 changes in quota distribution affected firms in different provinces differently. Unfortunately, the

lack of prefecture-level or county-level quota data prevents us from running regression discontinuity design (RDD) analyses.

Table 3: **Quota Regression**

	(1) OP	(2) LP
Post2003×QS	-0.0131*** (0.0012)	-0.0125*** (0.0012)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Firm Controls	Y	Y
Observations	708,637	708,637
R-squared	0.2288	0.2694

Notes: The dependent variables are firm productivity measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) and the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) methods. We use quota changes in each province as the treatment variable. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The set of firm-level control variables includes taxes paid and subsidies received by the firm. The standard errors are clustered at the prefecture level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

3.5 Robustness Checks

We implement eleven groups of robustness analyses to address an extensive set of potential empirical concerns for our main regression. The results are available in [Appendix A](#).

The first group addresses concerns with the robustness of our TFP estimates. We verify robustness by conducting the empirical analysis using firm-level TFP calculated with the methods proposed by [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#). [Table A1](#) shows that the results are very similar to the main results. The second group addresses concerns with the robustness of our bandwidth choice. We vary the bandwidths for the linear smoothing functions between 20 and 70 km in [Tables A2](#) and [A3](#). The results are very robust qualitatively. The third group addresses concerns with potential bad control issues. We estimate all main regressions without city-level lagged control variables to address any potential bad control issues. [Tables A4](#) and [A5](#) show that the resulting estimates are similar to those with control variables. Both the point estimates and R-squares exhibit minimal changes, validating our regression results according to [Oster \(2019\)](#). In

the fourth group, we simplify the regression discontinuity functional form by keeping the slope of the smoothing function unchanged at the boundary. Table A6 shows minimal change compared with the baseline results.

In the fifth group, we alleviate potential contamination from special geographical characteristics at the provincial boundary by excluding firms within 10 km on either side. Table A7 shows that the results are unchanged. In the sixth group, we investigate the effect of firms changing location. In Figure A1 and Table A8, we show that the number of relocating firms is minimal, and no regression results change if we drop these firms. This is reasonable since the National Industrial Enterprise Database firms are all "above scale" large firms that rarely change their locations. In the seventh group, we perform a placebo test by shifting the boundary to the west or the east. We do not observe significant changes in firm TFP gaps for these artificial boundaries before or after 2003, as shown in Table A9. In the eighth group, we change the clustering level of the standard error to the province level. Table A11 shows that the results are still statistically significant. However, considering the negligible sample size compared with the population, this high level of clustering is inappropriate (Abadie et al., 2020, 2023). In the ninth group, we drop Liaoning Province from our sample. Northeastern China enjoyed certain favorable policies for regional development and Liaoning was not restricted by the land supply policy after 2003. Table A12 shows that our results are robust to this change.

We also address concerns about possible confounders around 2003. In the tenth group of robustness checks, we address the potential spatial effect of China joining the WTO in 2001. To address this issue, we run regressions keeping only firms with zero exports and regressions controlling for firm-level exports to eliminate any WTO effect. The regression results in Tables A13, A14, A15, and A16 show that the main conclusions are unchanged. In the eleventh group, we try to rule out the effects of other subsidy and tax changes around 2003, which may distort our estimates. Tables A17, A18, and A19 show that the main results are maintained.

3.6 Remarks on Main Results

We show that the inland-favoring land policy decreased the firm productivity gap between developed eastern regions and underdeveloped inland regions. Based on the time trends of firm TFP in Figure 4, the relative changes are mainly due to reduced eastern firm productivity growth rather than improvements in inland productivity. These findings indicate that although the government achieved the goal of shrinking the eastern-inland gap, it potentially came at a substantial cost of distorting land prices and decreasing the productivity of eastern firms. In other words, such regional convergence comes at the cost of spatial misallocation. In the next section, we will investigate the mechanism at the firm level in more detail.

4 Mechanism Analysis

In this section, we further investigate the mechanism of the inland-favoring land policy on firm productivity. At the firm level, the policy influences TFP through two distinct channels. First, such a policy could directly damage the productivity of existing eastern firms by increasing production costs, decreasing R&D expenditure, reducing new firm entry, and consequently reducing regional agglomeration. We label this the "direct effect." Second, a more restrictive eastern land policy could precipitate the exit of lower productivity firms from the market, compel them to downscale their business below the survey threshold of the NIED, or even to cease operations. This could, in turn, elevate the average TFP of the location, a process we refer to as the "selection effect." Thus, it may offset part of the direct negative productivity effect of the policy. We aim to explore these two channels separately.

4.1 Direct Effect

First, we investigate the policy's direct effect on firm productivity by running the same main regression but using firms' factor inputs and total outputs as the dependent variables. By scrutinizing the input and output changes, we can determine why firm productivity fell in the east relative to the inland region. In Table 4, we consider five variables: return on assets in columns

(1) and (2); log of labor input (employment) in columns (3) and (4); log of capital input in columns (5) and (6); log of total output in columns (7) and (8); and log of R&D expenditure in columns (9) and (10). In the odd columns, we use a local linear smoothing function. In the even columns, we use a linear smoothing function.

Table 4: **RD-DID Results on Firm Inputs**

	ROA		Ln(Labor)		Ln(Capital)		Ln(Output)		Ln(R&D)	
	(1) LL	(2) Poly	(3) LL	(4) Poly	(5) LL	(6) Poly	(7) LL	(8) Poly	(9) LL	(10) Poly
Post2003×East	0.0132 (0.0110)	0.0057 (0.0064)	0.0229 (0.0715)	0.0327 (0.0280)	-0.0384 (0.0649)	-0.0655 (0.0476)	-0.0495 (0.0778)	-0.0855* (0.0468)	-0.1585** (0.0763)	-0.0906* (0.0532)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Observations	36,606	100,054	15,363	100,054	57,514	100,054	34,371	100,054	55,234	100,053
R-squared	0.0603	0.0475	0.0155	0.0125	0.0583	0.0547	0.1977	0.1736	0.0745	0.0779

Notes: The dependent variables are the return on assets, labor input, capital input, total output, and R&D expenditure, respectively. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD cases is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km around the raw boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

We find that after 2003, eastern firms reduced their output and R&D expenditures compared to their inland counterparts. No significant effects were observed for return on assets, labor input, and capital input. Consequently, we do not find evidence that the 2003 inland-favoring land policy led eastern firms to reduce their traditional labor and capital factor inputs. Rather, the primary factor behind the decrease in the relative TFP and output of eastern firms is the reduction in their R&D expenditures. Firms decide to sacrifice innovation when land is more expensive.

Besides this decline in R&D expenditure, the negative impact of the policy could also stem from diminished agglomeration. We additionally investigate the policy effect on firm entry using firm registration data. The dependent variable is the firm entry rate at the prefecture level, which is defined as the ratio of the number of newly entered firms to all existing firms in a prefecture. We keep only prefectures along the eastern-inland border and run a simple prefecture-level DID regression by controlling for prefecture and year fixed effects. Table 5 shows that the inland-favoring land policy led to more than a one percentage point decrease in the firm entry rate for

the eastern region. This effect is notably salient for the manufacturing sector. As less land supply and higher land prices raised the entry threshold, the agglomeration effect was reduced by the land-use policy. Reducing agglomeration and knowledge spillovers can also explain why firms are less incentivized to invest in innovation.

Table 5: **RD-DID Results on Firm Entry**

	All Firms		Manufacturing Firms	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Post2003×East	-0.0174*** (0.00515)	-0.0172*** (0.00512)	-0.0234*** (0.00624)	-0.0232*** (0.00609)
City Lagged Controls	N	Y	N	Y
Year FE	Y	Y	Y	Y
Prefecture FE	Y	Y	Y	Y
Observations	1,281	1,259	1,280	1,258
R-squared	0.162	0.183	0.154	0.189

Notes: The dependent variable is the proportion of newly-entered firms over all existing firms in a prefecture. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample includes only prefectures at the border of the eastern and inland regions. The standard errors are clustered at the prefecture level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

In Appendix B, we further analyze the first-order effect of the inland-favoring land policy on land prices using land parcel level transaction data collected from the China Land Market Website (<http://www.landchina.com/>). Using a simple difference-in-differences model, we find that the inland-favoring land policy widened the land price gap between eastern and inland regions by 50 percentage points. Therefore, firms in the eastern region respond to this massive land price increase by reducing their R&D expenditure to cut costs. The firm entry rate is also reduced.

4.2 Selection Effect

In the NIED dataset, we classify firms that are present in year t but absent from the survey in year $t + 1$ as exiting firms. Conversely, firms that are present in both years are categorized as surviving firms. Figure 6 illustrates the proportion of exiting firms relative to the total number of firms for each year. On average, the exit rate fluctuates between 10% and 20%, with inland firms more likely to exit. Notably, there was a significant spike in 2003, where the exit rate for firms in

both regions rose to over 25%.

Figure 6: Exit Rate of Firms from NIED

Notes: This figure shows the firm exit rate from the NIED Survey each year.

Figure 7 shows the average TFP for exiting firms (red solid line) and surviving firms (blue dashed line) across years. Subfigure (a) illustrates inland firms, and subfigure (b) illustrates eastern firms. We find that the productivity gap between exiting and surviving firms is smaller in the east than inland. Furthermore, the gap shrank by similar magnitudes after 2003 both inland and in the east. Therefore, there is no evidence in our data supporting a regional difference in the selection of firms after the 2003 inland-favoring land supply policy. The offsetting effect from the exit of firms with lower productivity does not exist. In Figures 8 and 9, we further investigate the trends of firms' total assets and employment. We detect no evidence for a larger positive selection of surviving firms in eastern regions after 2003.

To precisely estimate the changes in selective pressure for firm i in year t , we run the following Difference-in-Differences-in-Differences (DDD) regression:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Exit_{it} \times Post2003_t \times East_j + \beta_2 Exit_{it} \times Post2003_t + \beta_3 Post2003_t \times East_j + \beta_4 Exit_{it} \times East_j + \phi_i + \gamma_t + \beta_5 Exit_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

Figure 7: **TFP (OP) of Exiting and Surviving Firms by Region**

Notes: The data source is the National Industrial Enterprise Database. The blue dashed line represents surviving firms. The red solid line represents exiting firms. Subfigure (a) shows the TFP changes for inland firms. Subfigure (b) shows the TFP changes for eastern coastal firms.

Figure 8: **Total Assets of Exiting and Surviving Firms by Region**

Notes: The data source is the National Industrial Enterprise Database. The blue dashed line represents surviving firms. The red solid line represents exiting firms. Subfigure (a) shows the changes in total assets for inland firms. Subfigure (b) shows the changes in total assets for eastern coastal firms.

$Exit_{it}$ indicates whether firm i in year t is an exiting firm that will disappear in the next year's survey. β_1 is the parameter of interest, which evaluates whether the eastern-inland productivity gap between exiting and surviving firms changed after 2003. It represents the effect of the inland-favoring policy on firm selection. If we detect a significantly negative coefficient, it means that

Figure 9: **Employment of Exiting and Surviving Firms by Region**

Notes: The data source is the National Industrial Enterprise Database. The blue dashed line represents surviving firms. The red solid line represents exiting firms. Subfigure (a) shows the average employment changes for inland firms. Subfigure (b) shows the average employment changes for eastern coastal firms.

Table 6: **DDD TFP Selection Results**

	(1) OP	(2) LP
Exit×Post2003×East	-0.0152 (0.0183)	-0.0134 (0.0185)
Double Interactions	Y	Y
Exiting Dummy	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	805,906	805,906
R-squared	0.7061	0.7450

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) and the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) methods. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

this policy led to more selection and drove firms with low productivity growth out of the market in eastern regions, causing the remaining firms to have higher productivity growth than the firms who exited. Table 6 shows the results of this DDD regression, and we do not find any evidence for discrepancies in selection across regions.

4.3 Land Demand Heterogeneity

Finally, we provide further evidence for our mechanism by investigating the heterogeneity of the policy effect. We investigate the heterogeneous treatment effect across different industries with various land demands. If the mechanism we propose is true, we should expect firms in land-intensive industries to suffer more from the inland-favoring land policy since they are more sensitive to land price changes.

Table 7: **Heterogeneity Analysis on TFP**

	Across Industry	
	(1) Not Land Intensive	(2) Land Intensive
Post2003×East	-0.0459 (0.0524)	-0.0986** (0.0499)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	65,769	65,481
R-squared	0.1363	0.1053

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. In this table, we use local linear regression as the smoothing function. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

To investigate this issue, we calculate land demand intensity using Chinese Enterprise Tax Survey data. This reports land taxes paid by each firm, with which we can infer their land usage. Using this firm-level data, we then calculate the average land usage for each industry and define land-intensive industries as those with land usage above the median. Columns (1) and (2) in Table 7 show the results. We find that the impact of the inland-favoring land policy is much more significant for firms in land-intensive industries, both statistically and economically. This confirms that our proposed mechanism is true. Firms in land-intensive industries suffered more from the policy since they are more sensitive to land price changes.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we provide direct causal evidence of how China's 2003 inland-favoring land policy affected firm-level productivity by examining firms at the border of the eastern and inland regions. The inland-favoring land policy decreased the firm productivity gap between the more developed eastern regions and the underdeveloped inland regions. The relative changes are mainly due to the reduction in eastern firm productivity growth rather than growth in inland firm productivity. The mechanism analysis shows that the decrease in eastern firm productivity can be attributed to reduced R&D expenditure. This policy also deterred new firm entry in the eastern region, which shrunk agglomeration effects.

These findings indicate that although the government may have achieved the goal of shrinking the regional gap, it came at the cost of distorting markets, reducing eastern firms' productivity, and harming overall economic efficiency.

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A Robustness Checks

In this section, we implement nine groups of robustness checks for our empirical analysis. In the last subsection, we also investigate the policy effect on other outcome variables.

A.1 Robustness Checks for TFP Estimation Method

First, we implement the empirical analysis using firm-level TFP calculated using the method proposed by [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#). Table A1 shows the results of the primary regression using this productivity measure instead of the OP method, and all results remain very similar.

Table A1: **Robustness: RD-DID Results on TFP (LP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0533 (0.0478)	-0.0921** (0.0439)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	85,748	100,054
R-squared	0.1416	0.1493

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.2 Robustness Checks for Bandwidth Choices

Second, we adjust the bandwidth for the linear and quadratic smoothing functions. We present results for bandwidth choices ranging from 20 km to 70 km in Tables A2 and A3. The results remain qualitatively robust, although we lose observations when we reduce the bandwidth, leading to decreased estimation precision.

Table A2: **Robustness: TFP Regressions with Different Bandwidth Choices (OP)**

bandwidth	(1) 20km	(2) 30km	(3) 40km	(4) 50km	(5) 60km	(6) 70km
Post2003×east	-0.0235 (0.0682)	-0.0076 (0.0512)	-0.0761* (0.0426)	-0.0824** (0.0363)	-0.0574* (0.0330)	-0.0271 (0.0298)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Observations	39,747	72,488	100,054	126,265	152,064	184,678
R-squared	0.1303	0.1113	0.1161	0.1195	0.1208	0.1161

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. We use a linear fit as the smoothing function. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A3: **Robustness: TFP Regressions with Different Bandwidth Choices (LP)**

bandwidth	(1) 20km	(2) 30km	(3) 40km	(4) 50km	(5) 60km	(6) 70km
Post2003×east	-0.0056 (0.0694)	-0.0041 (0.0527)	-0.0921** (0.0439)	-0.0946** (0.0373)	-0.0688** (0.0341)	-0.0375 (0.0309)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Observations	39,747	72,488	100,054	126,265	152,064	184,678
R-squared	0.1644	0.1442	0.1493	0.1531	0.1547	0.1504

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. We use a linear fit as the smoothing function. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.3 Robustness Checks for No City-level Controls

Third, we run all main regressions without city-level lagged control variables for two reasons. First, although we use lagged city characteristics, there may still be a serial correlation with current period values, potentially leading to bad control issues. Second, this can also serve as a balance check. If dropping controls does not significantly change the point estimates, it suggests that the likelihood of omitted variable bias (in this case, location-period level unobserved variables) is low. Tables A4 and A5 demonstrate that the resulting estimates are similar to those in the regressions with control variables. The point estimates remain virtually unchanged. This implies that adding city characteristics does not affect the regression results, further validating the assumption that cities at the border have similar trends.

Table A4: **Robustness: TFP Regressions without City-level Controls (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0831** (0.0355)	-0.0701* (0.0425)
City Lagged Controls	N	N
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,250	100,054
R-squared	0.1157	0.1116

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2, except we drop all city-level lagged controls. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A5: **Robustness: TFP Regressions without City-level Controls (LP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0506 (0.0478)	-0.0867** (0.0438)
City Lagged Controls	N	N
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	85,748	100,054
R-squared	0.1374	0.1446

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2, except we drop all city-level lagged controls. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.4 Keeping Slopes Unchanged at the Boundary

Fourth, we change the regression specification to be more parsimonious by keeping slopes unchanged at the boundary. That is, we drop the fourth and the seventh terms in the main regression to have:

$$\ln(y_{ibct}) = \alpha + \beta_1 East_{ibt} + \beta_2 f(Dist_{ibt}) + Post2003 \times [\delta_1 East_{ibt} + \delta_2 f(Dist_{ibt})] + \beta_4 X_{ct-1} + \phi_{bt} + \gamma_t + \psi_i + \epsilon_{ibct} \quad (5)$$

Table A6 shows that this does not change our results. Our conclusion is not sensitive to the choice of the regression discontinuity functional form.

Table A6: **Robustness: RD-DID Results with No Slope Change (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0858** (0.0345)	-0.0761* (0.0416)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,250	100,054
R-squared	0.1202	0.1161

Notes: We keep the slopes unchanged around the boundary in this setting. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD case is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km around the raw boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.5 Thick Border

Fifth, following [Michalopoulos and Papaioannou \(2014\)](#)'s recommendation, we use a thick border in our regression analysis. Provincial borders are often formed by geographical features such as mountains or rivers, and firms at these boundaries may differ significantly from other firms. To address this, we exclude firms within 10 km of either side of the original provincial borders and extend our bandwidth by 10 km on the far sides of the border to preserve total bandwidth. This approach mitigates the potential impact of these unique geographic characteristics on our results. [Table A7](#) presents the results using a thick border, and there are no significant changes compared with our baseline setting.

Table A7: **Robustness: RD-DID Results with Thick Border (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0960 (0.0708)	-0.0961* (0.0509)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	79,668	111,595
R-squared	0.1076	0.1165

Notes: We drop all firms within 10 km of the boundary and create a thick border. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD case is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.6 Relocating Firms

Sixth, our empirical analysis is based on the National Industrial Enterprise Database, a panel dataset that tracks firm movements. However, a potential concern is that these relocation decisions may not be exogenous and could be influenced by the inland-favoring land policy. For instance, firms on the eastern side of the border may move to the other side of the boundary to take advantage of cheaper land. If the policy's effect on the local productivity gap is solely a result of this relocation, it may not have a meaningful impact on the economy as a whole.

Figure A1: **Number of Movers from 2001 to 2007**

Notes: This figure shows the number of firms relocating from eastern to inland regions and from inland to eastern regions in each year between 2001 and 2007.

Figure A1 illustrates the yearly count of companies relocating from eastern to inland regions and vice versa between 2001 and 2007 in our dataset. Generally, the number of relocating firms is minimal. For instance, only 3 out of 10,000 firms in our data moved from the east to inland in 2004. Additionally, we do not find any sudden change around the policy year 2003. Table A8 shows the main regression results when we drop all movers. There is no significant change.

Table A8: **Robustness: RD-DID Results without Movers (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0827** (0.0356)	-0.0754* (0.0427)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,749	99,953
R-squared	0.1198	0.1161

Notes: We drop all firms changing location. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD case is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.7 Placebo Test

In this section, we address the spatial spillover issue using two placebo tests. In the first placebo test, we move the boundary west and east to create alternate imaginary boundaries. Then, we compare firms on opposite sides of these imaginary boundaries using the main regression. If there are obvious spatial spillovers, that is if inland firms near the border were also negatively impacted by the policy, we should detect negative policy effects when we move the imaginary boundary to the west. Table [A9](#) shows no evidence for this.

In the second placebo test, we redefine the treatment and control groups. We drop all eastern firms and compare only inland firms. In column (1) of Table [A10](#), we consider inland firms within 5 km of the boundary as the treatment group and inland firms within 5 to 50 km of the boundary as the control group. In column (2) of Table [A10](#), we consider inland firms within 50 km of the boundary as the treatment group and inland firms within 50 to 100 km of the boundary as the control group. Essentially, we are taking inland firms located closer to the boundary as the treatment group and those located further from the boundary as the control group. We find that there are no statistically significant gaps between these groups.

Table A9: **Robustness: Moving Boundary Placebo Test (OP)**

	(1) West 50km	(2) West 100km	(3) East 50km	(4) East 100km
Post2003×East	-0.0204 (0.0647)	-0.0060 (0.0316)	-0.0215 (0.0186)	0.0139 (0.0142)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y	Y	Y
Observations	51,068	67,420	192,250	272,117
R-squared	0.7411	0.7363	0.7153	0.6968

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. In columns (1) and (2), we move the boundary to the west by 50 and 100 kilometers, respectively. In columns (3) and (4), we move the boundary to the east by 50 and 100 kilometers, respectively. We use a linear fit as the smoothing function and the bandwidth is 40 km. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A10: **Robustness: Moving Boundary Placebo Test II (OP)**

	(1) 0-5km vs 5-50km	(2) 0-50km vs 50-100km
Post2003×East	0.1224 (0.0748)	-0.1355 (0.0836)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	39,706	69,068
R-squared	0.7667	0.7603

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. In column (1), we compare inland firms within 5 km of the boundary with inland firms within 5 to 50 km of the boundary. In column (2), we compare inland firms within 50 km of the boundary with inland firms within 50 to 100 km of the boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.8 Clustering Standard Errors

In the main regression, we cluster the standard errors at the firm level, which is the cross-sectional unit of our panel data. This is recommended by Angrist and Pischke (2009) and Abadie et al. (2023). A potential concern is that firms located close to each other may be exposed to common shocks, which can result in spatial correlation of error terms. To capture this correlation, we cluster the standard errors at the province level. We estimate this regression after dropping all firms that changed location during the sampling period (movers) due to technical issues. Table A11 shows that we still have significant (or marginally significant) estimates. These estimates correspond to those in Table A8. We claim that this is a very conservative estimation of our standard errors because we have a dataset of all above-scale enterprises in China. If we do not consider our non-negligible sample size compared with the population, the standard errors are likely overestimated (Abadie et al., 2020). Clustering at too high a level is also not recommended by Abadie et al. (2023). Therefore, we cluster the standard errors at the firm level in our main regression.

Table A11: RD-DID Results on TFP (Clustering at Province-level)

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0827 (0.0503)	-0.0754* (0.0404)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,749	99,953
R-squared	0.1198	0.1161

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the Olley and Pakes (1992) method. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample in the polynomial RD cases is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km around the raw boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the province level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.9 Dropping Liaoning from the Sample

Ninth, we drop Liaoning Province from our sample. Since northeastern China also enjoyed certain other favorable policies for regional development, Liaoning was not restricted by the land supply policy after 2003. It is not accurate to categorize this province as either treated or part of the control group. Table A12 shows that our results are robust to this change.

Table A12: **RD-DID Results on TFP without Liaoning**

	(1) OP	(2) LP
Post2003×East	-0.0743* (0.0431)	-0.0922** (0.0444)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	96,523	96,523
R-squared	0.1157	0.1489

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) and the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) methods. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the scale of the service sector. We use a linear smoothing function with a bandwidth of 40km around the raw boundary in this regression. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.10 Robustness Checks for The WTO Effect

Tenth, China joined the WTO at the end of 2001, leading to significant changes in the country's economic structure. Despite occurring two years before the inland-favoring land supply policy, we remain concerned about potential confounding effects from the reduction in trade barriers, which may have influenced eastern and inland firms differently. To address this issue, we conduct the TFP regression using only firms with zero exports, as they should be the least affected by any WTO effects. Additionally, we run the main regression while controlling for firm-level exporting to eliminate any WTO-related influence. The regression results are displayed in Tables A13, A14, A15, and A16. Our main conclusions remain. We also find that a firm's exporting activity positively relates to its productivity, which aligns with predictions in the trade literature (Bernard et al., 2007, 2018).

Table A13: **Robustness: TFP Regressions without Exporting Firms (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0894** (0.0406)	-0.1079** (0.0487)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	105,161	79,951
R-squared	0.1229	0.1204

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the Olley and Pakes (1992) method. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2. We drop all firms with positive exports. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A14: **Robustness: TFP Regressions without Exporting Firms (LP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.1169** (0.0550)	-0.1395*** (0.0502)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	68,439	79,951
R-squared	0.1453	0.1533

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2. We drop all firms with positive exports. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A15: **Robustness: TFP Regressions Controlling for Exporting (OP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0719** (0.0355)	-0.0661 (0.0425)
log(Export)	0.0157*** (0.0013)	0.0160*** (0.0015)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,250	100,054
R-squared	0.1221	0.1181

Notes: We additionally control for firm-level exports in this regression. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. The regression specifications are otherwise identical to Table 2. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A16: **Robustness: TFP Regressions Controlling for Exporting (LP)**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0383 (0.0477)	-0.0760* (0.0436)
log(Export)	0.0253*** (0.0016)	0.0256*** (0.0015)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	85,748	100,054
R-squared	0.1465	0.1542

Notes: We additionally control for firm-level exports in this regression. The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. The regression specifications are otherwise identical to Table 2. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

A.11 Robustness Checks for Subsidy and Tax Policies

Eleventh, we attempt to rule out the effects of other concurrent subsidy and tax policies that may have been implemented alongside the land reform. Apart from the land supply policy, the Chinese government also enacted other inland-favoring measures to promote inland economic growth, such as manufacturing subsidies. We conduct the primary regression using firm-level government subsidies as the outcome variable to check whether relative subsidies changed for firms at the border during the same year the inland-favoring land policy was introduced. Table A17 indicates that firms on either side of the border received similar government subsidies before and after 2003. We then estimate the firm-level TFP regressions with additional controls, including city-level central government subsidies per capita, firm subsidies from the government, and firm-level taxes paid to the government. Tables A18 and A19 demonstrate that the main results remain consistent across all regression settings.

Table A17: **Robustness: RD-DID Results on Firm-level Subsidies**

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0034 (0.0022)	-0.0015 (0.0019)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	77,332	100,054
R-squared	0.0026	0.0023

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level subsidies. The set of lagged city-level control variables includes the log of GDP, the log of population, the log of city area, and the value added to the service sector. The sample in the local linear regression specification is restricted to be within an optimal bandwidth using a constant kernel. The sample for the polynomial RD case is restricted to be within a bandwidth of 40 km around the original boundary. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A18: RD-DID Results with Firm-level Subsidy and Tax Controls (OP)

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0728** (0.0339)	-0.0652 (0.0404)
Tax	-1.7408*** (0.0213)	-1.7556*** (0.0244)
Subsidy	-0.9215*** (0.0933)	-0.9819*** (0.1061)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	131,250	100,054
R-squared	0.2541	0.2534

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Olley and Pakes \(1992\)](#) method. We additionally control for firm-level subsidies and firm-level taxes in these regressions. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2. We drop city-level lagged controls. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table A19: RD-DID Results with Firm-level Subsidy and Tax Controls (LP)

	(1) Local Linear	(2) Poly RD (Poly=1)
Post2003×East	-0.0413 (0.0454)	-0.0810* (0.0416)
Tax	-1.7360*** (0.0274)	-1.7640*** (0.0250)
Subsidy	-0.9342*** (0.1242)	-0.9218*** (0.1110)
City Lagged Controls	Y	Y
Border FE	Y	Y
Year FE	Y	Y
Firm FE	Y	Y
Observations	85,748	100,054
R-squared	0.2712	0.2819

Notes: The dependent variable is firm-level TFP measured by the [Levinsohn and Petrin \(2003\)](#) method. We additionally control for firm-level subsidies and firm-level taxes in these regressions. The regression specifications are identical to Table 2. We drop city-level lagged controls. The standard errors are clustered at the firm level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

B Policy Effects on Land Prices

Our empirical strategy for analyzing land prices employs a DID regression at the land parcel level. Local land administration departments were required to publish information on the transfer of state-owned land-use rights only after the enactment of *The Regulations on the Disposition of State-Owned Land Use Rights for Auctions and Biddings* in 2007. Consequently, transaction data before 2007 is incomplete. The sample size became sufficient only after 2002; therefore, we conducted the regression using data from 2002 to 2007. Figures B1 illustrate the time trends for land prices. A significant increase in the land price gap between eastern and inland regions is observed after 2003. For land parcel i in prefecture j in year t , we estimate the following regression:

$$\ln(P_{ijt}) = \alpha + \delta_1 \text{Post2003}_t \times \text{East}_i + \phi_j + \gamma_t + \epsilon_{jt} \quad (6)$$

$\ln(P_{ijt})$ is the log land price. East_i indicates whether this land parcel is located in the eastern region. ϕ_j and γ_t are prefecture and year fixed effects, respectively. We further control for linear time trends in different provinces and prefectures with different initial period (2001) characteristics, including GDP per capita and industry composition. Table B1 presents the DID regression results. Our findings indicate that the inland-favoring land policy widened the land price gap between eastern and inland regions by 50 percentage points.

Figure B1: Land Price Time Trends

Notes: This figure shows land parcel price time trends. The black line is the average outcome value in the developed eastern region, and the grey line is the average outcome value inland. The dashed vertical line indicates the implementation of the inland-favoring land policy.

Table B1: DID Results on Land Prices

	(1)
Post2003×East	0.513** (0.220)
Province × Time Trend	Y
GDP Per Capita × Time Trend	Y
Industry Share × Time Trend	Y
Year FE	Y
Prefecture FE	Y
Observations	189,619
R-squared	0.502

Notes: The dependent variable is land parcel prices. We also control for land parcel level selling categories. The standard errors are clustered at the prefecture level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.